

Effects of a Brief Yoga Nidra Intervention on Stress, Anxiety, Depression, and Composite Cardiovascular Parameters in Patients with Essential Hypertension

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Essential hypertension (EH), or primary hypertension, is a common and chronic health condition worldwide and a significant risk factor for heart disease, stroke, and kidney disease. Often asymptomatic, it is known as a “silent killer”. In India, hypertension is a significant contributor to health-related issues, accounting for 57% of stroke deaths and 24% of deaths due to coronary heart disease. EH is primarily influenced by lifestyle factors, including workout, diet, stress, and sleep. Therefore, non-pharmacological interventions, such as yoga, diet, and stress management, aid in prevention and control. This study examines the effects of *yoga nidra* intervention on stress, anxiety, depression, mean arterial pressure (MAP), and rate-pressure product (RPP) in patients with EH. One hundred seventy-one male patients with EH from Nashik city were recruited (age range = 35 to 50 years, $M = 42.23$, $SD = 3.60$) and randomly assigned to either the *yoga nidra* or the control group. Guided *yoga nidra* sessions were conducted over 21 days, with one 1-hour session per day. Participants were tested at three time points-before, mid (11th day), and post-intervention using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (Zigmond & Snaith, 1983) and the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1983). Cardiovascular measures, including blood pressure (BP) and heart rate (HR), were recorded. Standard Gain score analysis revealed that *yoga nidra* (YN) significantly reduced participants' stress, depression, and anxiety. Furthermore, cardiovascular parameters like MAP (Diastolic Pressure + 1/3 (Systolic Pressure-Diastolic Pressure) and RPP (HR x systolic BP) decreased significantly, indicating improved cardiovascular function following the brief YN intervention. Detailed findings and implications are discussed.

Keywords: Yoga nidra, stress, essential hypertension, depression, anxiety, cardiovascular health

Essential hypertension (EH) has become a prominent health issue in India, contributing significantly to the burden of mortality and illness. Recently, it has become a particularly significant non-infectious disease, affecting both rural and urban populations. Roughly 25% of the urban adult population and 10% of the rural population are affected by EH (Bhupatiraju et al., 2012). Annually, hypertension is responsible for approximately 1.1 million deaths, accounting for over half (57%) of all stroke deaths and nearly a quarter (24%) of all coronary heart disease deaths, i.e., 10.8% of all deaths (Jadon, 2024).

According to studies, the incidence of hypertension varies by region and demographics, ranging from 9.3% to 47.9% among different populations. These findings highlight the impact of lifestyle variables, including high salt intake, tobacco use, and physical inactivity (Prathyusha et al., 2016). Sedentary lifestyles, age, high body mass index (BMI), and dyslipidemia have become risk factors for EH in urban areas (Gogoi et al., 2020). The cases of

hypertension surged from 600 million in 1980 to 1 billion in 2008, which was a dramatic increase (Jadon, 2024). Targeted interventions and lifestyle modifications are key factors in managing and mitigating the impact of essential hypertension, as highlighted by these findings.

Psychological Correlates of EH

Mental health disorders like depression, stress, and anxiety are often associated with EH. Aguirre-Palacios and Jaramillo-Montaña (2024) systematically reviewed 11 studies published between 2019 and 2024. They were able to find that people who experience EH show a high occurrence of these psychological issues, with anxiety ranging between 25% to 100%, depression from 5.2% to 64.1%, and stress from 60% to 71.5%. According to their observation, the relationship between EH and these disorders emerges to be bidirectional. These findings underscore the complex relationship between psychological well-being and physical health.

Cardiovascular Markers and Autonomic Dysfunction in EH

Heart rate (HR) and blood pressure (BP) are complexly linked to EH, with substantial implications for cardiovascular risk. Research suggests that irregularities in acceleration capacity (AC) and deceleration capacity (DC) are linked to impaired nocturnal systolic BP decrease, which indicates potential autonomic dysfunction in individuals with hypertension (Wang et al., 2024). Additionally, sympathetic nervous system (SNS) activation is triggered by a critical biomarker, which is elevated HR. This strongly correlates

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with cardiac noradrenaline spillover, an important indicator of cardiac sympathetic activity (Esler et al., 2020). Remarkably, risk of adverse cardiovascular outcomes has been independently linked to figures of resting HR more than 80 beats per minute (Kishi, 2020). Thus, in clinical management of EH, constant monitoring and management of cardiovascular markers such as HR and BP are crucial.

Psychophysical Interactions: The Role of Stress, Anxiety, and Depression

The complex relationship between stress, anxiety, and depression strongly impacts HR and BP, thereby raising the risk of EH. Studies conducted by Lutin et al. (2022) and Sanchís-Gomar and Lippi (2024) found that individuals who experience anxiety and depression often show increased HR and BP, mainly due to physiological processes such as heightened SNS activation and diminished HR variability. A meta-analysis has shown that depression is linked to a 46% higher risk of developing cardiovascular disease, whereas anxiety aggravates cardiovascular morbidity (Sanchís-Gomar & Lippi, 2024). Additionally, disruptions in the circadian regulation of HR are often linked to chronic stress and depression, particularly when they occur together (Lutin et al., 2022). These findings underscore the crucial importance of comprehensive treatment strategies that encompass both psychological and physical aspects (Sanchís-Gomar & Lippi, 2024; Zhang, 2024). Increasingly, the management of hypertension involves both standard medications and non-pharmacological strategies, such as lifestyle adjustments and yoga (Ahuja et al., 2024).

Yoga Nidra as Mind-Body Intervention

Among the many yoga techniques, YN is a supine, guided meditation practiced in shavasana that is intended to induce complete mental, physical, and emotional relaxation, and often is referred to as 'yogic sleep' (Hoye & Reddy, 2016; Ahuja et al., 2024). By activating the body's rest and relaxation state, YN creates autonomic nervous system changes that lower HR and BP. Its practice offers several benefits for both mental and physical health, including reduced anxiety and stress, improved sleep, and resynchronization of the circadian rhythm (Ahuja et al., 2024). It gained popularity due to its multiple benefits, effectiveness, safety, and ease of doing (Hoye & Reddy, 2016; Musto & Vallerand, 2023).

Research Gap and Study Objectives

Despite these cited central investigative studies and other peripherally related studies, there is insufficient conclusive evidence on the efficacy of YN on EH management and its impact on biomarkers such as HR and BP. Very few studies have been conducted on the effects of YN on composite cardiovascular parameters of BP and HR, like MAP and RPP. Thus, this study aims to investigate the impact of brief YN intervention on stress, anxiety, depression, and composite cardiovascular parameters (MAP & RPP) in patients diagnosed with EH.

Hypotheses of the Study

It was hypothesized that the YN (treatment) group would show greater improvement than the control group in stress (H1), anxiety (H2), depression (H3), MAP (H4), and RPP (H5).

Method

Participants

A total of 171 male patients with essential hypertension (EH) from Nasik city were recruited (age range = 35-50 years, $M=42.23$, $SD=3.60$).

Measures

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS; Zigmond & Snaith, 1983) and the *Perceived Stress Scale (PSS; Cohen et al., 1983)* were used to measure anxiety, depression, and stress, respectively. Cardiovascular parameters were recorded using a standardized digital sphygmomanometer under resting conditions, including systolic and diastolic blood pressure (BP) and resting heart rate (HR).

Procedure

Participants were randomly assigned to either the *yoga nidra* or the control group. The *yoga nidra* group received guided *yoga nidra* meditation sessions for 21 consecutive days. Each session lasted approximately 60 minutes and was conducted daily between 10:00 and 11:00 a.m. (± 30 minutes). The sessions were delivered as per Swami Satyananda Saraswati's standardized protocol. Participants were instructed to refrain from consuming tea, coffee, or caffeinated drinks at least 3 hours before the intervention. All sessions were conducted in a quiet environment with participants lying down in *śavāsana* (corpse pose) to ensure comfort and minimal physical movement. The control group received no intervention during this period but continued with their usual routine.

Outcome measures were assessed at three time points-baseline (pre-intervention), mid-intervention (11th day), and post-intervention (21st day). Psychological variables were measured using the *Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS; Zigmond & Snaith, 1983)* and the *Perceived Stress Scale (PSS; Cohen et al., 1983)*. Cardiovascular parameters were recorded using a standardized digital sphygmomanometer under resting conditions, including systolic and diastolic blood pressure (BP) and resting heart rate (HR). All assessments were conducted between 8:00 a.m. and 10:00 a.m. (± 30 minutes), approximately two hours prior to the YN session, to control for circadian variations. All participants provided written informed consent prior to enrollment in the study. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality of the data was assured.

Statistical Analyses

Standard gain scores analyses were conducted using an independent samples t-test for stress, anxiety, depression, MAP, and RPP variables.

Results

As a part of data screening methods, firstly, outliers were removed from the data using boxplots (summaries of separate variables). In this process, the initial sample size of 200 participants (100 in the treatment group & 100 in the control group) dropped to 171, with 88 participants in the treatment group and 83 participants in the control group. Standard gain scores of stress, anxiety, depression, MAP, and RPP were normally distributed, with the skewness ranging from a minimum of 0.09 to a maximum of 0.52, and kurtosis ranging from a minimum of -0.86 to a maximum of -0.10 (Table 1). Both skewness and kurtosis were within the acceptable range of -1.00 to +1.00 and -2.00 to +2.00, respectively (Byrne, 2016; George & Mallery, 2021; Hair et al., 2018).

Table 1
Skewness and Kurtosis for Study Variables

Variable	N	Skewness	Skewness SE	Kurtosis	Kurtosis SE
Std GS Stress	171	0.0981	0.186	-0.855	0.369
Std GS Anxiety	171	0.5193	0.186	-0.101	0.369
Std GS Depression	171	0.2583	0.186	-0.512	0.369
Std GS MAP	171	0.3347	0.186	-0.423	0.369
Std GS RPP	171	0.4387	0.186	-0.436	0.369

Note. Std GS = Standard Gain Score = ((Posttest - Pretest) ÷ Pretest) × 100. SE = Standard error

Following the data screening, standard gain score analyses were employed to assess the impact of the YN intervention. It was ensured that the assumptions for the independent samples t-test were met for the same. Table 2 presents descriptive statistics for the study

variables in the treatment and control groups, organized by test. Table 3 presents descriptive statistics for the standard gain score of study variables in the treatment and control groups. Table 4 provides for standard gain score analyses (independent samples t-tests).

Table 2
Test-wise Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables in Treatment and Control Groups

Variable	Group	N	M	SE	SD
Stress Pre	Treatment	88	13.97	0.561	5.26
	Control	83	12.95	0.514	4.68
Stress Post	Treatment	88	7.84	0.309	2.90
	Control	83	11.46	0.444	4.05
Anxiety Pre	Treatment	88	7.01	0.385	3.62
	Control	83	5.87	0.288	2.63
Anxiety Post	Treatment	88	4.07	0.221	2.07
	Control	83	5.61	0.288	2.63
Depression Pre	Treatment	88	5.65	0.304	2.85
	Control	83	5.18	0.231	2.11
Depression Post	Treatment	88	3.28	0.174	1.63
	Control	83	5.00	0.202	1.84
MAP Pre	Treatment	88	102.40	0.404	3.79
	Control	83	100.64	0.548	4.99
MAP Post	Treatment	88	100.63	0.402	3.77
	Control	83	100.95	0.525	4.78
RPP Pre	Treatment	88	10652.03	128.938	1209.55
	Control	83	10545.83	136.726	1245.64
RPP Post	Treatment	88	10039.14	115.781	1086.12
	Control	83	10245.41	137.275	1250.63

Note. SE = Standard Error of Mean. SD = Standard deviation.

Table 3
Std Gain Score Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables in Treatment & Control Group

Variable	Group	N	M	SE	SD
Std GS Stress	Treatment	88	-41.83	1.695	15.90
	Control	83	-10.688	1.539	14.03
Std GS Anxiety	Treatment	88	-40.48	1.611	15.11
	Control	83	-3.521	2.114	19.26
Std GS Depression	Treatment	88	-38.09	2.089	19.60
	Control	83	-0.349	2.208	20.11
Std GS MAP	Treatment	88	-1.72	0.158	1.48
	Control	83	0.323	0.150	1.36
Std GS RPP	Treatment	88	-5.57	0.527	4.94
	Control	83	-2.765	0.544	4.95

Note. Std = Standard. SE = Standard Error of Mean. SD = Standard deviation.

Table 4*Standard Gain Score Analyses (Independent Samples t-tests) for Study Variables*

Variable	t	df	M diff	SE diff	Cohen's d
Std GS Stress	13.55**	169	-31.14	2.298	-2.073
Std GS Anxiety	13.90a**	155	-36.95	2.658	-2.135
Std GS Depression	12.43**	169	-37.74	3.037	-1.901
Std GS MAP	9.37**	169	-2.04	0.218	-1.434
Std GS RPP	3.70**	169	-2.80	0.757	-0.567

Note. Std = Standard. SE = Standard Error of Mean. SD = Standard deviation. a. Levene's test is significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting violation of the assumption of equal variances. Thus, Welch's t is used for the anxiety variable. Cohen's d = 0.2 small effect; 0.5 moderate effect; 0.8 large effect size (Cohen, 1998). ** $p < 0.01$.

The results indicate significant differences between the YN treatment group and control group for all psychological and cardiovascular measures, viz., stress, anxiety, depression, MAP, and RPP.

The YN treatment group exhibited a significant stress reduction ($M = 41.83 \pm 15.90$) compared to the control group ($M = 10.69 \pm 14.03$), with an independent samples t-test showing a significant difference with a large effect size, $t(169) = 13.55, p < 0.01$, Cohen's $d = 2.073$. Similarly, anxiety levels in the YN treatment group significantly reduced ($M = 40.48 \pm 15.11$) compared to the control group ($M = 3.52 \pm 19.26$), Welch's $t(155) = 13.90, p < 0.01$, Cohen's $d = 2.135$. Depression also showed a substantial decrease in the YN treatment group ($M = 38.09 \pm 19.60$) compared to the control group ($M = 0.35 \pm 20.11$), $t(169) = 12.43, p < 0.01$, Cohen's $d = 1.43$. Thus, H1, H2, and H3 were accepted.

In case of cardiovascular measures, the YN treatment group exhibited a significant decrease in MAP ($M = 1.72 \pm 1.48$) compared to the control group ($M = 0.32 \pm 1.36$), $t(169) = 9.37, p < 0.01$, Cohen's $d = 1.43$. The RPP also showed a significant reduction in the YN treatment group ($M = 5.57 \pm 4.94$) compared to the control group ($M = 2.77 \pm 4.95$) with a moderate effect size, $t(169) = 3.70, p < 0.01$, Cohen's $d = 0.57$. Thus, H4 and H5 were accepted.

Discussion

The findings suggest that the YN intervention had a significant impact on reducing the levels of stress, anxiety, and depression in patients suffering from EH. The large effect sizes observed for stress and anxiety indicate that the intervention was highly effective in managing and alleviating mental health concerns among the EH patients. Similar findings were observed in depression, except the effect size was moderate.

Both stress and anxiety are state-dependent and thus generally are more reactive to interventions. Also, stress and anxiety are closely linked to hyperactivity in the sympathetic nervous system (e.g., increased HR, BP, & cortisol levels). Depression is also linked to physiological changes but often involves neurochemical imbalances (e.g., serotonin & dopamine deficiencies) and thus takes longer to normalize. This explains the moderate effect size in the case of depression and the large effect sizes for stress and anxiety.

These findings are consistent with the earlier studies. Yoga has been shown to lower stress (Chiesa & Serretti, 2010) and malondialdehyde, a hallmark of oxidative stress, additionally raising the presence of antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase

(Zope & Zope, 2013). There is sufficient evidence supporting how yoga and sleep alleviate psychological symptoms of mental stress, anxiety, and depression (Brown & Gerbarg, 2005; Nagendra et al., 2012; Mohan et al., 2023; Sengupta, 2012; Makarem et al., 2021). Specific studies on YN also found that YN induces a state of deep relaxation, activating the parasympathetic nervous system (PNS), which in turn helps lower cortisol levels, thereby reducing stress (Chaudhary & Kumar, 2024). Nayak and Verma (2023) and Malviya et al. (2023) also concluded that YN effectively reduces anxiety and depression, making it a complementary approach to traditional therapies. Our study specifically assessed the efficacy of YN intervention on stress, depression, and anxiety among EH patients, highlighting its distinctive contribution to the existing literature.

Composite cardiologic outcomes such as MAP and RPP also showed significant improvements in the YN treatment group compared to the control group. Reduction in MAP and RPP suggests that YN can help in managing EH in addition to the benefits it provides to the patients in reducing stress, anxiety, and depression. The reduction in MAP shows that the intervention has improved cardiovascular health, potentially managing the EH symptoms. Similarly, a reduction in RPP indicates a reduced myocardial workload, a critical factor in cardiovascular health management. Although the effect size for RPP is moderate, it is important to note that the intervention was conducted over a relatively short duration (21 days). Given the limited timeframe, even a moderate effect size for reducing RPP represents a meaningful and clinically relevant finding.

Our findings are consistent with those of the earlier studies. The YN's technique mainly triggers a relaxation response, which increases parasympathetic activity and lowers the sympathetic activity (Ahuja et al., 2024). Therefore, YN mainly affects the brain by promoting neuronal system relaxation (Pandi-Perumal et al., 2022; Parker et al., 2013). YN lowers peripheral vascular resistance and PB by reducing sympathetic overactivity and regulating HR (Reboussin et al., 2018; Pandi-Perumal et al., 2022). Additionally, it has a secondary advantage of lowering BP by addressing the mental health issues of HT patients, such as stress, anxiety, and depression (Reboussin et al., 2018). Amarasekera and Chang (2019) conclude that, like meditation, YN may also help lower vascular inflammation, which would lower BP.

Conclusion, Limitations, and Future Suggestions

We observed a significant overall effect of brief YN intervention in

managing psychological concerns such as stress, anxiety, and depression, and composite cardiovascular measures such as MAP and RPP among 171 EH patients (treatment group = 88; control group = 83). The present study confirms that YN can be an alternative complementary approach to traditional therapies to manage EH. YN does not require physical asanas or postures and can be performed easily in a reclining position. Thus, it can prove to be an appealing, inexpensive, relatively easy, and safe therapy technique for the important global concern of EH. Due to its ease of performing, it can be an ideal therapy technique for elderly persons.

Nevertheless, there is currently a paucity of research confirmation available, and additional trials are required to generalize these results. Further research on long-term YN intervention is needed with a rigorous experimental approach and additional tools for quantifying the YN program's psychological, physiological, neurological, and endocrinological effects. Furthermore, extended follow-up periods and larger, more diverse samples can provide robust evidence of YN's efficacy in managing EH.

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